

Mediating Effect of Teaching Passion on Managerial Behavior and Career Enthusiasm of Teachers

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Abstract. This study investigated the mediating effect of teaching passion on the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm among public secondary school teachers in Davao City, Philippines. Anchored on the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory, Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory, and Passion Investment Theory, the research explored how effective managerial practices influence teachers’ enthusiasm for their profession, both directly and through their intrinsic passion for teaching. Using a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design, the study involved 251 teachers randomly selected from Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools. A researcher-made and expert-validated questionnaire with high reliability (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.934$) was administered. Statistical tools such as mean, Pearson correlation, Baron and Kenny’s (1986) mediation method, and the Sobel z-Test were applied to analyze the relationships among the variables. Results showed that managerial behavior and teaching passion were rated as moderately extensive, while career enthusiasm was found to be extensive, indicating that teachers often display professional motivation though inconsistently across all domains. Correlation results revealed strong and significant positive relationships among managerial behavior, teaching passion, and career enthusiasm ($r = 0.716\text{--}0.816$, $p < 0.05$). Mediation analysis confirmed that teaching passion partially mediates the link between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm, with both direct and indirect effects found significant ($z = 10.96051$, $p < 0.001$). The findings suggest that supportive and inspiring managerial practices enhance teachers’ enthusiasm not only through direct influence but also by fostering deeper teaching passion. The study concludes that cultivating passion among teachers serves as a vital mechanism for translating leadership support into lasting motivation, engagement, and professional fulfillment. It recommends that educational leaders and policymakers design programs that strengthen teachers’ passion and well-being to promote sustained career enthusiasm and instructional excellence.

KEY WORDS

1. managerial behavior 2. teaching passion 3. career enthusiasm 4. teacher motivation

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1. Introduction

Teachers today face serious challenges with low motivation and declining commitment to their teaching responsibilities. This is often reflected in their reduced energy, which weakens their classroom performance and overall effectiveness. In addition, many teachers ex-

perience limited professional growth, as they lose interest in pursuing training or developing new skills. These conditions also lead to a weakened sense of fulfillment in the profession, making it harder for them to sustain enthusiasm for their career. Such problems highlight the importance of examining how teaching passion mediates the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm, which will be further discussed in the succeeding paragraphs. In Africa, classrooms remain challenged by teachers' minimal initiative to adjust lessons based on learners' cultural and linguistic backgrounds. Mabena et al. (2021) reported that many African teachers continue to deliver uniform lessons, leaving students unable to connect with what is taught. She further noted that this practice reduces learners' engagement and widens gaps among those from disadvantaged groups. Mboweni and Taole (2022) stated that the lack of contextualized teaching worsens inequalities in education. They also highlighted that students in under-resourced schools are the most affected, as their diverse experiences are rarely reflected in lessons. In Dubai, the growing presence of expatriate students has exposed problems in adapting lessons to diverse cultural backgrounds. Samways et al. (2019) explained that many teachers rely on rigid, standardized approaches that fail to respond to multicultural classrooms. Accordingly, this leads to feelings of exclusion among learners from minority groups. Alhajji (2020) presented that students in Dubai struggle when their cultural realities are not acknowledged in teaching. They also noted that this lack of contextualization results in reduced classroom participation and weaker academic performance. In Thailand, issues persist as teachers show minimal adjustments to lessons due to strict adherence to the national curriculum. Cornwall and Monroe (2023) reported that many classrooms in Thailand remain tied to rigid teaching plans, which disconnect students from real-life applications. It was also noted that this practice reduces interest, particularly for students in rural areas. Prabjandee (2019) highlighted that ignoring learner backgrounds weakens motivation among Thai students. They further stated that this issue limits the development of participatory skills and hinders critical engagement in learning. Taking things in Philippine setting, particularly in Luzon, problems are evident as teachers often neglect socio-economic and linguistic differences among students. Fabelico and Afalla (2020) reported that a one-size-fits-all approach to instruction creates inequities in Luzon classrooms. It was also observed that learners from lower-income families are more likely to feel disengaged when lessons lack contextual adjustments. Lobo (2023) noted that the absence of culturally responsive teaching weakens inclusivity in Luzon schools. He further noted that this issue leaves students less motivated to engage meaningfully in classroom activities. In the Mindanao, the problem continues due to limited training and insufficient resources for contextualizing instruction. Bayod et al. (2021) pointed out that teachers with weak pedagogical content knowledge are less likely to adjust lessons to meet learners' needs. The author also noted that this gap reduces the effectiveness of instruction in diverse classrooms. Madid et al. (2024) reported that the neglect of learners' backgrounds disrupts the scaffolding process essential for building new knowledge. The author further explained that such conditions restrict opportunities for progressive learning among students. At the local level in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City, the problem is visible in the uniformity of lessons delivered by teachers. Failure to differentiate instruction results in reduced participation among learners in local classrooms. This limitation further affects academic growth and weakens student engagement. Culturally unresponsive teaching also remains a barrier to inclusive learning in these classrooms. As a result, many students

often feel unseen, which negatively affects their motivation and overall achievement. There are noticeable gaps in the existing literature on the connection between managerial behavior, teaching passion, and career enthusiasm of teachers. From a temporal perspective, many of the available studies were conducted years ago and do not fully reflect the present challenges teachers face in a changing educational system. In terms of methodological gaps, most works have focused on qualitative or mixed-methods approaches, which provide descriptive insights but lack the statistical strength to establish patterns and mediating effects. Furthermore, an empirical gap is evident because very few studies directly examine teaching passion as a mediator between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm, particularly in the Philippine context. These gaps point to the need for a more updated, quantitative, and context-specific study. The urgency to conduct this study in Cluster 15 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City lies in the growing concerns about teacher motivation, classroom management, and long-term career dedication. Teachers in this setting face multiple pressures such as high workloads, limited resources, and changing demands, which may weaken their enthusiasm for the profession if not supported by passion. By examining teaching passion as a mediator, the study can provide evidence-based insights on how managerial behavior translates into sustained career enthusiasm. The findings will be socially relevant as they can guide school leaders and policymakers in designing professional development and support systems tailored to the local context. Thus, this study may contribute to building a motivated and committed teaching workforce in the district.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is anchored on the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory by Demerouti et al. (2001) which explains how job demands (such as workload and classroom man-

agement) and job resources (such as administrative support and passion for teaching) influence employee well-being and performance. It highlights that the balance of demands and resources shapes motivation, engagement, and retention. In relation to the study, the JD-R theory is appropriate because it shows how teachers' managerial behavior (a form of job demand) interacts with teaching passion (a motivational resource). This balance then influences career enthusiasm, especially in challenging school environments. Therefore, the theory helps explain how passion serves as a mediator that transforms work pressures into motivation rather than burnout. In support, Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory by Hobfoll (2011) suggests that individuals strive to obtain, retain, and protect resources, such as energy, skills, and emotional investment. When resources are gained, motivation and engagement increase; when resources are lost, stress and disengagement occur. This theory is suitable because teaching passion can be seen as a valuable emotional resource that teachers draw upon when fulfilling their managerial roles. With passion, teachers can transform management tasks into meaningful work, thus preserving their enthusiasm for the career. Consequently, the theory supports the idea that passion mediates the relationship by acting as a protective resource against loss of energy or motivation. Moreover, Passion Investment Theory by Vallerand et al. (2003) states that passion represents a strong inclination toward activities that people love, find important, and invest time and energy in. It distinguishes between harmonious passion, which promotes balance and well-being, and obsessive passion, which may lead to burnout. This theory directly fits the study since it explains how teaching passion can fuel sustained engagement and balance in professional tasks. Teachers with harmonious passion can align their managerial behavior with personal values, leading to stronger career enthusiasm. Thus, the theory clarifies why passion

can serve as a mediating variable that transforms routine management into sustained professional joy. As shown in Figure 1, this study consists of three variables. The independent variable is the managerial behavior which refers to the various actions, strategies, and approaches teachers use to create and maintain an effective learning environment. The measures of managerial behavior are model way or the leadership concept that emphasizes the importance of leading by example and setting a positive role model for others to follow; inspire a shared vision or the leadership concept that involves articulating a compelling and inspiring vision for the future and rallying others around it; challenge the process or the leadership concept that involves questioning the status quo, experimenting with new ideas, and seeking innovative solutions to improve outcomes; enable others to act or the leadership concept that emphasizes empowering and supporting others to achieve their full potential; and encourage the heart or the leadership concept that emphasizes the importance of recognizing and celebrating the contributions and

achievements of others. The dependent variable of this study is the career enthusiasm of teachers refers to the strong sense of purpose, intrinsic motivation, and a deep-seated belief in the importance of education and its transformative power. The measures of career enthusiasm of teachers are compensation or the financial and non-financial rewards and incentives that educators receive for their work, which can impact their motivation, job satisfaction, and overall enthusiasm for teaching; external forces or the factors outside of teachers' direct control that can influence their motivation, job satisfaction, and overall enthusiasm for teaching; motivation to teach or the internal drive, passion, and commitment that educators have towards their profession and their students; and school culture or the shared values, beliefs, norms, and practices that shape the overall climate and atmosphere within a school community. Lastly, the mediating variable is teaching passion or the strong sense of purpose, intrinsic motivation, and genuine dedication to fostering student learning and development.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, ethical consideration, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher will utilize quantitative research specifically descriptive-correlational technique to gather data ideas, facts and information related to the study. Quantitative research design referred to a systematic inquiry that used numerical data to measure variables and analyze relationships among them. It focused on objectivity, precision, and statistical evidence to provide valid and reliable conclusions (Fischer et al., 2023). This design was appropriate for the study because it allowed the researcher to measure levels of managerial behavior, teaching passion, and career enthusiasm numerically.

It also provided a basis for testing the mediating effect of teaching passion with statistical rigor. Furthermore, it ensured that the findings were generalizable across teachers in Cluster 15 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. On one hand, descriptive research methods referred to approaches that systematically described the current status or characteristics of a population or phenomenon. These methods emphasized “what is” rather than establishing cause-and-effect (Siedlecki, 2020). The descriptive method was appropriate as it enabled the study to present clear descriptions of teachers' managerial behavior, levels of teaching passion, and

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

degree of career enthusiasm. It provided baseline data that clarified the state of these variables within the study setting. In addition, it helped frame the relationships among variables in a way that was easy to interpret and useful for practical application. On the other hand, correlational research approach referred to a method that examined the statistical relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It identified whether variables were positively or negatively related and to what extent (Sullivan, 2024). This approach was appropriate because the study sought to determine the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm and how teaching passion functioned between them. It allowed the researcher to analyze the strength and direction of these relationships using actual data. Moreover, it provided evidence on whether higher levels of managerial behavior were associated with higher levels of career enthusiasm. Moreover, Baron and Kenny's (1986) mediation method referred to a statistical framework that tested whether a third variable, called the mediator, explained the relationship between an independent and a dependent variable. The Sobel z-Test complemented this method by testing the significance of the indirect effect. This method was appropriate because the study examined whether teaching passion mediated the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm. It clarified whether managerial behavior influenced career enthusiasm directly or indirectly through passion. Furthermore, the Sobel z-Test provided statistical confirmation of the mediation effect, strengthening the validity of the findings.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—Ethical considerations were essential in ensuring that the rights, dignity, and welfare of all research respondents are protected throughout the study. This section outlines the ethical principles and procedures that will guide the conduct of the research to uphold integrity, transparency, and

responsibility.

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were 251 teachers from Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This number was determined using the Slovin Formula with a margin of error of 0.05, taken from a total population of 670 teachers. The formula ensured that the sample size was adequate to represent the entire population. Through this process, the researcher was able to balance the accuracy of the findings with the practicality of data gathering. As a result, the 251 teachers served as a reliable sample for the study. The respondents were selected using the simple random sampling technique. This method was defined as a process in which every member of the population had an equal chance of being chosen. It was also defined as a probability-based sampling procedure that minimized bias in respondent selection (Noor et al., 2022). In the process, the researcher assigned numbers to all teachers in the population list and used a random generator to select the required sample. This ensured fairness, accuracy, and equal opportunity for all teachers to be included in the study. The researcher also set clear inclusion criteria in choosing the respondents. Only teachers who were currently employed in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools during the conduct of the study were included. Respondents were required to have at least two years of teaching experience to ensure familiarity with managerial behavior, teaching passion, and career enthusiasm. Teachers on extended leave or those with administrative designations were excluded since they were not directly engaged in full classroom instruction. By applying these criteria, the researcher ensured that the sample was both relevant and appropriate to the objectives of the study.

2.4. Research Instrument—The study made use of researcher-made survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. It was pilot tested in a nearby school and was expected

to obtain a Cronbach’s alpha value greater than 0.700, indicating that the questionnaires had a high level of internal consistency. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subjected to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments. The questionnaire is composed of three parts. The first part is about the managerial behavior which is composed of statements which is in-

dicated with model the way, inspired a shared vision, challenge the process, enable others to act, and encourage the heart. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. The Cronbach alpha value for the new scale is 0.934, described as excellent and interpreted as highly reliable. As a guide in determining the extent of managerial behavior, the researcher made use the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

Descriptive Interpretation of Teachers’ Managerial Behavior

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The managerial behavior of the teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The managerial behavior of the teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The managerial behavior of the teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The managerial behavior of the teachers is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The managerial behavior of the teachers is never observed.

Descriptive Interpretation of Teachers’ Career Enthusiasm

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The career enthusiasm of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The career enthusiasm of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The career enthusiasm of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The career enthusiasm of teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The career enthusiasm of teachers is never manifested.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure—*

Descriptive Interpretation of Teachers’ Teaching Passion

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teaching passion of teachers is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teaching passion of teachers is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teaching passion of teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teaching passion of teachers is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teaching passion of teachers is never evident.

Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire.

Permission to Conduct the Study

The process of securing permission to conduct the study began with obtaining an official endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. This endorsement served as the formal approval that the study was academically aligned with the institution’s standards and objectives. After securing this endorsement, the researcher proceeded to apply for ethical clearance from the Graduate School RMC–Research Ethics Committee (GSRMC-REC). This clearance was vital in ensuring that the study complied with established ethical principles such as respect, confidentiality, and fairness in dealing with respondents. Through these steps, the researcher demonstrated academic responsibility and adherence to ethical guidelines. Following these approvals, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City to conduct the study in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools. To strengthen the request, the endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School and the ethical clearance from the GSRMC-REC were attached to the formal communication. This process highlighted

transparency and accountability in gaining access to the research setting. Adding more, the submission of complete documents ensured that the conduct of the study was both authorized and properly supported by academic and ethical institutions. In this way, the researcher secured legitimate entry into the schools while respecting institutional protocols.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire

The first step in the data gathering process was the careful selection of the respondents from Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Using the identified sampling method, the researcher ensured that the chosen teachers accurately represented the population. Before the main data collection, a pilot test was conducted among a small group of respondents not exceeding 30 teachers. This pilot test was done to check the clarity, validity, and reliability of the survey questionnaire. The results of the pilot test guided necessary revisions to improve the instrument before its actual use. After finalizing the questionnaire, the distribution phase was implemented systematically. The respondents were properly oriented regarding the purpose of the study and the importance of their honest responses. They were also informed that they would be given ample time to complete

the survey, ensuring that they could reflect carefully on their answers. This process reduced pressure and allowed respondents to respond thoughtfully. Completed questionnaires were then collected and checked for completeness to ensure accuracy of the data gathered. Moreover, flexibility in answering the questionnaire was observed by allowing respondents to choose between online and face-to-face modes. Online forms were shared with those who preferred digital submission, while printed copies were provided to teachers who were more comfortable with traditional methods. This approach respected the varying preferences and access to resources among respondents. The retrieval of both online and physical questionnaires was done with confidentiality, ensuring the protection of the respondents' identity. In this way, the distribution and retrieval process was carried out efficiently and ethically.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data

After the collection of all completed survey questionnaires, the first step was to carefully count and sort the responses to ensure completeness and accuracy. The data were then systematically recorded in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet, where responses were organized according to the domains of managerial behavior, career enthusiasm, and teaching passion of teachers. This process provided an initial structure that facilitated easier handling and preparation of data for analysis. By coding and categorizing the responses properly, errors were minimized, and the dataset became ready for statistical procedures. Thus, collation ensured that the information gathered was accurate, organized, and suitable for analysis. Following collation, descriptive statistics were employed to provide a clear overview of the data. The statistical mean was computed to describe the extent of managerial behavior, career enthusiasm,

and teaching passion of teachers. This analysis allowed the researcher to identify whether these variables were reflected at low, moderate, or high levels within the respondent group. Descriptive statistics provided essential baseline insights into the general patterns present in the data. Consequently, the findings established the foundation for deeper analysis using inferential tools. After the descriptive phase, inferential statistics were applied to examine the relationships among the variables. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between managerial behavior, teaching passion, and career enthusiasm. To test mediation, Baron and Kenny's (1986) Method of Mediation Analysis was conducted, supported by the Sobel z-Test to confirm the significance of the indirect effects. These inferential tools enabled the researcher to determine whether teaching passion mediated the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Hence, this phase of analysis provided evidence-based findings beyond descriptive observation. Finally, the results of both descriptive and inferential analyses were interpreted and discussed comprehensively. The researcher related the findings to existing literature and theoretical frameworks to explain their significance. Practical implications were also highlighted, emphasizing how results could be used to strengthen teacher development and administrative support. Based on the findings, the researcher formulated recommendations to guide school leaders, policymakers, and future researchers. Therefore, the interpretation and recommendation stage ensured that the study contributed both academically and practically to the educational community.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—

The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data:

Mean

This was useful in characterizing the managerial behavior, career enthusiasm, and teaching passion of teachers in Cluster 13 Public secondary Schools in Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation

It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship among independent (managerial behavior), dependent (career enthusiasm), and mediating (teaching passion) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear

relationship between paired data. In a sample it is usually denoted by r .

Baron and Kenny's (1986) Method for Mediation Analysis

It was applied to evaluate the mediating effect of teaching passion on the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of the teachers in Cluster 13 Public secondary Schools in Davao City.

Sobel z-Test

This was used to determine the significance on the mediating effect of teaching passion on the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of the teachers in Cluster 13 Public secondary Schools in Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of managerial behavior, career enthusiasm, and teaching passion of teachers; the significant relationship among these variables; and the mediating effect of teaching passion on the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of teachers in Cluster 15 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

3.1. Managerial Behavior of Teachers—

The managerial behavior of teachers in this study is measured in terms of model the way, inspire a shared vision, challenge the process, enable others to act, and encouraging heart. The extent of this variable and its domain is presented on the succeeding table. Summary on the Managerial Behavior of Teachers

On Table 1, the overall mean for the managerial behavior of teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City is 3.30, interpreted as moderately extensive. This indicates that while teachers sometimes demonstrate lead-

ership practices across different domains, such behaviors are not yet consistently embedded in their daily routines. The moderately extensive rating reflects a developing but uneven application of managerial behaviors, suggesting that teachers are still in the process of strengthening their leadership roles in the classroom. As highlighted by Liebowitz and Porter (2019), moderate levels of leadership practices reveal a need for stronger reinforcement and institutional support. Likewise, Tindowen (2019) emphasized that developing consistent leadership practices is crucial to building a supportive and high-performing school culture.

Among the domains assessed, Challenge the Process and Enable Others to Act both received the highest mean of 3.42, interpreted as extensive, indicating that teachers oftentimes take

initiative in innovation and collaboration to improve teaching and learning. In contrast, Model the Way registered the lowest mean at 3.18, interpreted as moderately extensive, suggesting

Table 1. Summary on the Managerial Behavior of Teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Model The Way	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Inspire a Shared Vision	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Challenge the Process	3.42	Extensive
Enable Others to Act	3.42	Extensive
Encourage the Heart	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.30	Moderately Extensive

that teachers are less consistent in setting personal examples and adhering to leadership values. This pattern reflects that while collaboration and innovation are actively pursued, the personal embodiment of leadership principles may require additional attention and development. Echoing the view of Sakız et al. (2020), the balance of modeling values and encouraging collaboration is critical to sustaining leadership effectiveness among teachers.

3.2. *Career Enthusiasm of Teachers*—The career enthusiasm of teachers in this study is measured in terms of compensation, external forces, motivation to teach, and school culture. The extent of this variable and its domain is presented on the succeeding table. Summary on the Career Enthusiasm of Teachers On Table 2, the overall mean for the career enthusiasm of teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City is 3.48, interpreted as extensive. This indicates that teachers oftentimes display enthusiasm in their profession through adequate compensation, external support, strong motivation, and positive school culture, though some aspects remain moderately evident. The extensive rating suggests that while teachers generally maintain a high level of professional drive,

targeted reinforcement is still needed in certain areas to ensure sustained career fulfillment. According to Kasalak and Dağyar (2021), career enthusiasm is a crucial factor in teacher retention and effectiveness, yet it requires consistent support from institutional and community structures. In line with this, Karakış (2021) emphasized that enthusiasm reflects both emotional and professional commitment, which significantly impacts teaching quality. Among the assessed domains, External Forces received the highest mean of 3.61, interpreted as extensive, suggesting that teachers oftentimes gain motivation from parental support, job opportunities, and community partnerships. In contrast, Motivation to Teach recorded the lowest mean at 3.36, still within the moderately extensive category, indicating that while teachers recognize their impact on students, their intrinsic motivation may sometimes waver due to professional challenges. This pattern reflects the observation of Pourshafei and Jafari (2024), who noted that external and organizational supports often strengthen teacher morale, whereas internal motivation may be more vulnerable to stress and workload pressures.

3.3. *Passion of Teachers*—Summary on the Teaching Passion of Teachers On Table 3, the mean for the teaching passion of teachers in

Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City is 3.38, interpreted as moderately extensive. This suggests that teachers sometimes

Table 2. Summary on Career Enthusiasm of Teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Compensation	3.44	Extensive
External Forces	3.61	Extensive
Motivation to Teach	3.36	Moderately Extensive
School Culture	3.49	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.48	Extensive

demonstrate strong passion and commitment toward the profession, but such dedication is not consistently manifested in all aspects of their work. The moderately extensive rating points to a developing but uneven expression of teaching passion, which signals the need for supportive interventions to sustain enthusiasm. As stressed

by Vallerand et al. (2023), passion for teaching serves as an intrinsic motivator that enhances teacher effectiveness and resilience. In support, Yu and Ying (2024) explained that cultivating passion in teaching is critical in maintaining high levels of instructional quality and career satisfaction.

Table 3. Summary on Teaching Passion in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Perceiving oneself as highly committed to the teaching profession.	3.55	Extensive
Lying awake at night while thinking ahead to the next day’s work responsibilities.	3.41	Extensive
Enjoying teaching as a meaningful and fulfilling profession.	3.04	Moderately Extensive
Contemplating that even with equal pay in another job, choosing teaching would still be the preference.	3.86	Extensive
Reflecting that even if given another chance, still choosing to work in the teaching profession.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
Feeling proud to have entered the teaching profession.	3.44	Extensive
Mean	3.38	Moderately Extensive

The individual mean scores for this domain range from 2.99 to 3.86, spanning moderately extensive to extensive ratings. The highest-rated

statement is Contemplating that even with equal pay in another job, choosing teaching would still be the preference, with a mean of 3.86, showing

that teachers oftentimes perceive teaching as a personally meaningful calling despite external alternatives. On the other hand, the lowest-rated statement is Reflecting that even if given another chance, still choosing to work in the teaching profession, with a mean of 2.99, suggesting that teachers sometimes reconsider their career choice due to challenges in the profession. This finding echoes the insights of Kirkpatrick et al. (2024), who observed that teachers' passion may fluctuate depending on workload, recogni-

tion, and available support systems.

3.4. Relationship Among Managerial Behavior, Career Enthusiasm, and Teaching Passion of Teachers—The results on the analysis on the relationship among managerial behavior, career enthusiasm, and teaching passion of teachers are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned.

Table 4. Relationship Among Managerial Behavior, Career Enthusiasm, and Teaching Passion of Teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Variables	Career Enthusiasm (r)	Teaching Passion (r)	p-value
Managerial Behavior	0.816**	0.716**	0.000
Career Enthusiasm	1	0.693**	0.000

Note. **Significant at $p < 0.05$. Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$.

The findings reveal a strong and significant positive relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of teachers ($r = 0.816$, $p = 0.000$), resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that teachers who observe effective managerial behaviors from their leaders are more likely to sustain higher levels of enthusiasm in their profession. According to Karakış (2021), supportive and consistent leadership behaviors strongly influence teacher morale and career satisfaction. Likewise, Polizzi Filho and Claro (2019) emphasized that managerial practices that highlight guidance, fairness, and encouragement enhance teachers' enthusiasm and professional engagement. There is also a strong and significant positive relationship between managerial behavior and teaching passion ($r = 0.716$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that effective leadership behaviors from administrators and heads are closely associated with the teachers' intrinsic motivation and passion for teaching. Chou and

Sun (2024) asserted that when leaders demonstrate fairness, trust, and vision, teachers are more likely to feel valued and inspired in their work. Similarly, Onyeabor et al. (2024) found that strong managerial support fosters teacher passion, resilience, and commitment to teaching responsibilities. Lastly, the results show a strong and significant positive relationship between career enthusiasm and teaching passion of teachers ($r = 0.693$, $p = 0.000$), prompting the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that teachers who maintain higher enthusiasm in their profession are also more likely to demonstrate stronger teaching passion. Zhang (2019) explained that enthusiasm and passion are inter-related factors that reinforce teachers' motivation, persistence, and dedication to their work. In support, Serin (2023) emphasized that enthusiastic teachers who find fulfillment in their careers are more likely to sustain passion, which translates into improved instructional quality and positive student outcomes.

3.5. *Mediating Effect of Teaching Passion on the Relationship Between Managerial Behavior and Career Enthusiasm of Teachers*—The results on the analysis on the mediating effect of teaching passion on the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of teachers in Cluster 15 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City is shown in Table 5. The path coefficients table reveals a significant and positive direct relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of teachers, with an estimate of 0.784, a z-value of 14.104, and $p < .001$. This indicates that effective managerial behavior directly contributed to higher levels of career enthusiasm, particularly in terms of motivation, satisfaction, and professional fulfillment. In addition, teaching passion significantly predicted career enthusiasm (estimate = 0.229, $z = 4.763$, $p < .001$), while managerial behavior strongly predicted teaching passion (estimate = 0.828, $z = 17.581$, $p < .001$). The presence of this mediating variable highlights that managerial behavior not only directly enhanced career enthusiasm but also indirectly influenced it by strengthening teachers' passion for teaching. The parameter estimates further confirmed a partial mediating effect. The indirect effect of managerial behavior on career enthusiasm via teaching passion was significantly positive (estimate = 0.190, $z = 4.597$, $p < .001$), while the direct effect remained strongly significant at 0.784 ($z = 14.104$, $p < .001$). The total effect stood at 0.974 ($z = 24.190$, $p < .001$), indicating that although teaching passion enhanced the influence of managerial behavior on career en-

thusiasm, managerial behavior itself remained the primary driver of improvement. This means that supportive leadership and strong managerial practices boosted teacher enthusiasm both directly and through the cultivation of passion for teaching. The ratio index of 0.1950 and the Sobel z-test value of 10.96051 ($p = 0.0000026$) provided strong statistical evidence of a partial mediation effect. The positive ratio confirmed that teaching passion enhanced rather than diminished the direct relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm. Practically, this implied that when teachers' passion was nurtured, they were more likely to channel the positive effects of managerial behavior into higher enthusiasm and sustained professional commitment (Ho et al., 2021). These findings offer strong support for the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory by Demerouti et al. (2001), which affirms that adequate resources such as strong leadership increase motivation and engagement, aligning with how managerial behavior and teaching passion fostered career enthusiasm. They also resonate with the Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory by Hobfoll (2011), as teachers who preserved and enhanced their resources through administrative support and passion demonstrated higher professional fulfillment. Likewise, the results support the Passion Investment Theory by Vallerand et al. (2003), which underscores that passion drives sustained effort and motivation; in this case, teaching passion amplified the effects of managerial behavior on career enthusiasm rather than contradicting it.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

Table 5. Mediating Effect of Teaching Passion on the Relationship Between Managerial Behavior and Career Enthusiasm of Teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Path Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
<i>Step 1: MB → CE</i>	0.784	0.056	14.104	<.001
<i>Step 2: TP → CE</i>	0.229	0.048	4.763	<.001
<i>Step 3: MB → TP</i>	0.828	0.047	17.581	<.001
Step 4: Parameter Estimates				
Indirect Effect Components: MB → TP → CE	0.190	0.041	4.597	<.001
Direct Effect: MB → CE	0.784	0.056	14.104	<.001
Total Effect: MB → CE	0.974	0.040	24.190	<.001

Note. Ratio Index = 0.1950; Sobel z-Test value = 10.96051, $p = 0.0000026$. MB = Managerial Behavior; CE = Career Enthusiasm; TP = Teaching Passion.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to explore the mediating effect of teaching passion on the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm of teachers in Cluster 13 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City through the methods of Mediation by Baron and Kenny (1986) utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 251 public secondary school teachers drawn from a total population of 670 in the said cluster of schools as the respondents through stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The result of the study are summarize as follows: The managerial behavior of teachers in Cluster 13 public secondary schools in Davao City is assessed as moderately extensive, suggesting that teachers sometimes display leadership practices across the five domains but do not consistently apply them in all situations. Among the domains, Challenge the Process and Enable Others to Act are the most evident, showing teachers' inclination toward innovation and collaboration. In contrast, Model the Way is the least observed, indicating that teachers need stronger consistency in setting personal examples and embodying leadership values. Career enthusiasm is generally rated as extensive, indicating that teachers oftentimes show positive motivation and fulfillment in their profession. External forces emerged as the strongest dimension, suggesting that community partnerships, job stability, and parental support significantly boost teachers' enthusiasm. On the other hand, motivation to teach is the least evident, showing that intrinsic drive is not always strong, with some teachers experiencing wavering commitment due to professional challenges. Teaching passion is assessed as moderately extensive, suggesting that teachers sometimes show strong passion for their profession, but this is not consistently manifested across all indicators. Teachers are most likely to affirm their preference for teaching despite alternative career options, reflecting a sense of vocation. However, reflecting that they would still choose teaching if given another chance is the least observed, indicating that challenges in the profession sometimes diminish their passion. The correlation analysis reveals strong and significant positive re-

relationships among managerial behavior, career enthusiasm, and teaching passion. All pairwise relationships are statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses. These findings indicate that effective managerial practices directly strengthen career enthusiasm and teaching passion, while enthusiasm and passion also reinforce each other in sustaining teachers' professional commitment. The mediation analysis confirms that teaching passion significantly mediates the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm, with the indirect effect enhancing the direct path. Although managerial behavior remains the strongest predictor of career enthusiasm, teaching passion amplifies its influence by reinforcing teachers' motivation and professional fulfillment. These results affirm the importance of leadership support in cultivating passion, which in turn sustains teacher enthusiasm and strengthens retention.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: The managerial behavior of teachers in Cluster 13 public secondary schools was found to be moderately extensive, showing that teachers sometimes demonstrate leadership practices but not consistently across all domains. The most evident practices were enabling others to act and challenging the process, while modeling the way was the least practiced, suggesting uneven leadership application. This implies that professional development should focus on strengthening consistency in modeling values and personal leadership practices to build stronger role models for students. Career enthusiasm among teachers was rated as extensive, indicating that they oftentimes show positive motivation and fulfillment in their profession. External forces such as community support and job stability were the strongest contributors, while motivation to teach was the least evident, reflecting wavering intrinsic drive. This suggests the need for strategies that balance

external supports with efforts to sustain teachers' inner commitment to teaching. Teaching passion was found to be moderately extensive, showing that teachers sometimes express strong commitment but this passion is not always sustained across all situations. The highest-rated indicator reflected teaching as a vocation despite external alternatives, while reconsideration of the profession if given another chance was the least evident. This implies that systemic challenges in the profession must be addressed to maintain and strengthen teachers' long-term passion for their work. The correlation analysis revealed strong and significant positive relationships among managerial behavior, career enthusiasm, and teaching passion. This suggests that effective leadership practices not only enhance enthusiasm but also reinforce teachers' passion, and that both constructs are interdependent in sustaining professional commitment. The implication is that interventions to strengthen school leadership will have a multiplier effect by simultaneously increasing passion and enthusiasm among teachers. The mediation analysis confirmed that teaching passion significantly mediates the relationship between managerial behavior and career enthusiasm, with both direct and indirect effects found to be strongly positive. This result supports the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory by Demerouti et al. (2001) and the Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory by Hobfoll (2011), as leadership support and passion acted as resources that enhanced teacher motivation. It also supports the Passion Investment Theory by Vallerand et al. (2003), showing that passion amplifies the effects of managerial behavior on enthusiasm, underscoring the importance of nurturing passion as a mediating factor in teacher retention and effectiveness.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are offered to inform policy, school leadership, teaching practice, and future research:

For DepEd Officials. DepEd officials may strengthen policies and programs that provide consistent leadership training and professional growth opportunities for teachers to enhance managerial behavior. They can allocate resources for initiatives that promote teacher enthusiasm and passion, such as recognition programs and wellness support. They may also institutionalize monitoring systems to ensure that leadership practices and career motivation are addressed at both the local and regional levels.

For School Heads. School heads may implement supportive and transparent managerial practices that inspire teachers' passion and sustain their career enthusiasm. They can encourage collaboration, provide timely feedback, and ensure that necessary resources are available to carry out teaching responsibilities effectively. They may also create a school culture where innovation and passion are celebrated, which can positively influence teacher commitment and performance.

For Teachers. Teachers may continuously enhance their teaching passion by engaging in reflective practices and seeking professional growth opportunities. They can foster career enthusiasm by building supportive relationships with colleagues, parents, and the community. They may also actively participate in leadership initiatives and model positive behaviors that contribute to a stronger teaching-learning environment.

For Future Researchers. Future researchers may explore similar studies in other school clusters or regions to validate and expand the findings of this study. They can also examine additional variables such as teacher resilience, work-life balance, or instructional innovation to provide deeper insights. They may employ longitudinal or mixed-method approaches to capture the long-term effects of managerial behavior, passion, and enthusiasm on teacher retention and effectiveness.

5. References

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